

Analysis of the Effectiveness of the Village Cash for Work (PKTD) Program in Gianyar Regency

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Abstract:- This study was conducted in Gianyar Regency with a sample size of 88 respondents using purposive sampling method. Data collection was carried out using a survey approach through questionnaires and in-depth interviews. This study employed descriptive statistical tests to examine the respondents' perceptions and Wilcoxon signed-rank test to analyze the difference in income before and after the implementation of the PKTD Program. The results of the study indicate that the income after the implementation of PKTD Program is higher compared to the income before the implementation of the PKTD Program and the effectiveness level of the program implementation is considered highly effective. The weaknesses of the PKTD Program lie in the lack of training and skill development, as well as the lack of commitment and seriousness in implementing the program. The study also reveals weaknesses in the PKTD program, particularly in terms of training and skill development for the community, as well as a lack of commitment in program implementation. Therefore, further efforts are needed to enhance training, integrate training programs, and strengthen the community's understanding and commitment to The Village Cash For Work Program.

Keywords:- Effectiveness, Village Cash For Work Program, Village Fund, Income.

I. INTRODUCTION

The high rate of poverty is one of the factors that can hinder a country's economic development (Kuncoro, 2015). Thus, poverty becomes an important problem that needs special attention to be overcome for a country. This poverty is a big problem that is also experienced by Indonesia as one of the developing countries. A global problem facing many countries, poverty is a complex problem. The target rate of decline in the number of poor people is the main indicator of the success of development efforts in a region. Poverty can be seen from the backwardness, unemployment and helplessness of a society. There are three strategies that can be done to overcome this poverty phenomenon, namely empowerment, social assistance, and providing business credit assistance (Putra & Sri Budhi, 2015).

Poverty in Indonesia can be divided into urban poverty and rural poverty. Figure 1 illustrates that the number of poor people in Indonesia is mostly concentrated in rural areas. This is not much different from the picture of poverty in Indonesia that exists so far, where development programs implemented tend to be biased towards urban areas.

Fig. 1: Infographic on Poverty Profile in Indonesia, September 2022

Figure 1 shows that the percentage of rural poor is higher than that of urban poor with a percentage of 12.36% for rural areas and 7.53% for urban areas or as many as 14.38 million people for rural areas and 11.98 million people for urban areas in September 2022.

To overcome these problems, at this time local governments are given autonomy, freedom to determine how to develop their regions in accordance with the potential of existing natural and human resources by involving as much community participation as possible in accordance with applicable laws (Wiagustini, 2017). With a high percentage of poor people in rural areas, Indonesia disburses village

funds, which are expected to be utilized by village governments in financing governance, village development, and village community empowerment. Law Number 6 of 2014, Article 78 paragraph (1) reads: village development aims to improve the welfare of rural communities and the quality of human life as well as poverty reduction through meeting basic needs, building village facilities and infrastructure, developing local economic potential, and sustainable use of natural resources and the environment.

The existence of Law No. 6 of 2014 which is the legal umbrella of the Village Fund is expected to be able to reduce rural poverty, in its implementation the ineffective use of Village Funds does not have an impact on poverty alleviation (Rimawan, 2019). This Village Fund is expected to be able to improve public services in villages, advance the village economy, alleviate poverty, overcome development gaps between villages and strengthen rural communities as subjects of development. This Village Law mandates village governments to be more independent in managing their government and various natural resources, including financial management (village funds) and village-owned wealth.

Several programs have been carried out by the government to help reduce poverty. Village funds are one of the breakthroughs that are expected to help overcome problems regarding income inequality and poverty in rural areas. As recommended by the President, the allocation of village funds must increase from year to year. Especially for areas that have the potential to develop such as Gianyar Regency.

Gianyar Regency is one of the areas that has high tourism potential and potential in small industrial activities, although Gianyar Regency has been supported by the tourism sector and small industrial activities that can improve the economy, but classic problems such as poverty still occur. The poverty rate that occurs in Gianyar Regency is an increasing trend for the last few years which shows that the government has not been fully successful in tackling poverty. With the implementation of the village law, poverty is still quite high, especially the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic which has shaken the overall economy since the end of 2019.

Table 1: Number of Poor People in Gianyar Regency in 2019-2021

Years	Number of Poor People (People)	Percentage of Poor People (%)
2019	19.850,00	3,88
2020	21.010,00	4,08
2021	25.360,00	4,85

Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) of Gianyar Regency (2022)

Based on Table 1 according to data from the Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) of Gianyar Regency 2022, the number of poor people in Gianyar Regency has increased from 2019 to 2021, reaching 25,360.00 residents. This can mean that the problem of poverty in the region has increased in that time span. This increase in the number of poor people shows that there is an inequality in income distribution and welfare in Gianyar Regency. This data also indicates the need for greater and targeted efforts in poverty reduction efforts in Gianyar District.

The Government of the Community and Village Empowerment Office of Gianyar Regency recorded that there were 719 PKTD program recipients in Gianyar Regency in 2022. The PKTD program has targeted several villages in 7 sub-districts in Gianyar Regency and there are 26 villages that meet the provisions of PKTD, namely village activities that meet the minimum wage requirement of 50% (fifty percent) of the Village Cash Intensive activity fund. The following is data on the number of PKTD program recipients in Gianyar Regency in 2019-2022.

In Indonesia, including Gianyar Regency, during a pandemic like today, the use of Village Funds has been prioritized for handling COVID-19. Corona-Virus-Disease 2019 has caused casualties, and greater material losses, which has implications for economic, social, and community welfare aspects. The use of Village Funds has been prioritized for handling COVID-19 with activities in the form of Covid-19 response Villages, Village Cash For Work, and Village Fund Cash Direct Assistance (General Guidelines for the Use of Village Funds in 2022).

As the implementer of the village fund program, the village government plays an important role in carrying out community development and empowerment. The village government plays a role in providing facilities and infrastructure and designing activities that are expected to increase community independence so that they have the skills, knowledge, and ability to utilize resources through the Village Fund priority program.

The PKTD program as an empowerment program that utilizes local resources, labor and technology with the program targets being unemployed, poor families, and marginalized communities is a priority program by the government in efforts to alleviate poverty in rural areas. By seeing that one of the main causes of poverty is the lack of community empowerment and with the existence of programs that can absorb a lot of local labor, this PKTD program is expected to be able to reduce poverty rates in rural areas.

In managing village funds, a village assistance team was formed so that they could manage village funds properly and could minimize unintentional mistakes. The village assistant will supervise the village government in managing village funds, starting from program preparation, implementation, evaluation to program reporting.

One of the most important things in measuring the success of a program. Effectiveness, can be seen from how far the achievement of results (output) from the planned goals, stated by Martani and Lubis (1987: 55) there are three approaches to measure effectiveness, namely: a) Resource

approach measures the effectiveness of inputs, b) Process approach, which looks at the effectiveness of programs from all process activities or organizational mechanisms, c) Goals approach, which measures the success of the organization to achieve results (outputs) in accordance with the plan. According to Gibson (2000), one of the main conclusions of systems theory about effectiveness criteria is that effectiveness criteria must describe the entire cycle of inputs – processes – outputs, not just outputs. According to systems theory, the effectiveness of a program or organization cannot be measured solely on the basis of the results or outputs produced. It is important to consider the entire work cycle involving inputs, processes, and outputs. In this context, input refers to the resources used in the execution of the program, process refers to the way the program is executed, and output refers to the results produced. In evaluating effectiveness, it is necessary to pay attention to the extent to which the program utilizes resources efficiently (input), how the program is executed (process), as well as the results produced (output). This means that the definition of effectiveness is the achievement of the results of the goals set, This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of the implementation of PKTD program in Gianyar Regency and to analyze the income conditions of the poor before and after the implementation of the program, and finally, where each policy program must have weaknesses in its implementation. Therefore, the PKTD program needs to be evaluated to assess how effective the implementation of the program in Gianyar Regency is. The main focus in this study is the effectiveness of the Village Cash For Work (PKTD) program in Gianyar Regency, especially in improving development and community empowerment in Gianyar Regency.

Based on this background description, the purpose of this study is to analyze the condition of community income before and after the implementation of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency; To analyze the effectiveness of the implementation of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency; and to analyze the weaknesses found in the implementation of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

A. Theory of Economic Development

A country's economic development succeeds with three core values: the development of people's ability to meet their basic needs (sustenance); increased self-esteem of people as human beings; and increased ability of people to choose (freedom from servitude) The perspective regarding the primary goal of economic development efforts is no longer focused solely on achieving high economic growth, but rather on reducing poverty and inequality rates (Arsyad, 2015).

B. Poverty Theory

According to Kartasmita (in Dalimoenthe, 2023), impoverished communities generally have limited abilities to engage in economic activities and limited access to economic opportunities, causing them to fall far behind other communities with higher potential. Meanwhile, Soemardjan (in Sumodingrat 1999:81) elaborates on various methods of measuring poverty, while still considering two categories of poverty levels. Absolute poverty refers to a condition where

an individual's income is insufficient to meet their basic needs, while relative poverty is calculated based on the income distribution proportion within a region or between social strata.

C. Empowerment Theory

Conceptually, empowerment can be interpreted as an effort to improve the dignity of people who are unable to escape the device of poverty. Empowering is empowering and self-reliant communities. Community empowerment is not only a reinforcement of individuals, but also includes its institutions, namely instilling values in society such as hard work, openness, and frugality. Mardikanto and Soebiato (2015) argue that efforts to empower the community can be done in three ways, first, namely enabling, creating an atmosphere that allows the development of community potential, where basically the community has potential that can be developed, empowerment efforts can be done by raising awareness of rural communities to develop their potential. Second, strengthening the potential of the community with concrete and positive steps such as providing access to various opportunities. Third, protecting the weak, empowering means advocating for the weak to prevent imbalanced competition and exploitation of the weak by the strong.

D. Revenue Concept

One of the main concepts most often used in measuring the economic condition of a person or household is income level. According to Sukirno (2006), income is a number of people's income for their work performance both daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly. Furthermore, Rahardja and Manurung (2001) distinguish income into economic income, money income, and personal income. When viewed from the way it is obtained, according to Tohar (2003) income can be divided into two, namely gross income, income obtained before deducting expenses and net income, income obtained after deducting expenses.

E. Impact of Productive Assistance for Micro Enterprises (BPUM) on MSME Profits in Gianyar Regency

Based on the description of the main problem, literature review and discussion of previous research, hypotheses can be formulated that are used as references in solving the main problem. The formulation of problems regarding effectiveness and weakness is not described in the form of hypotheses because the discussion is carried out descriptively. Research problems using hypotheses can be formulated as follows:

- H0: There is no difference in income before and after the implementation of the PKTD Program
- H1: Income after the implementation of the PKTD Program is greater than the income before the implementation of the PKTD Program.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is comparative, that is, this study was conducted to compare how the income condition of the program recipient community before and after the implementation of the PKTD program. The study also used descriptive analysis, namely this study was conducted to

explain the effectiveness of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency from input, process, and output indicators as well as weaknesses contained in the implementation of the Village Cash For work (PKTD) program in Gianyar Regency.

This research was conducted in Gianyar Regency. The choice of location is based on the fact that Gianyar Regency is one of the areas that has the potential to develop, Gianyar Regency is one of the areas that has high tourism potential and potential in small industrial activities, although Gianyar Regency has been supported by the tourism sector and small industrial activities that can improve the economy, but classic problems such as poverty still occur. Several programs have been carried out by the government to help reduce poverty. Village funds are one of the breakthroughs implemented, with the implementation of the village law regarding the PKTD program, based on these conditions, the author is motivated to examine how the effectiveness of the Village Cash For work (PKTD) program in Gianyar Regency.

A. Object of study

The objects of this study are the effectiveness of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency, the income conditions of recipient communities before and after the implementation of the PKTD program, and the weaknesses of the implementation of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency:

- Community Income Variables. Community Income Variable is the variable of Changes in Income Level.
- Program success variables. The variables of program success in this study are input, process to output variables. Input variables consisting of the implementation of program socialization, the level of target accuracy, the accuracy of the amount of wages. Process variables consisting of monitoring implementation, companion response speed, and PKTD program acceptance requirements. Output variables consisting of achieving program objectives, distributing program assistance and utilizing PKTD programs.

B. Variable Operational Definition

The operational definition of community income variable is income before the implementation of the PKTD program and after the implementation of the PKTD program. Income can be measured in terms of the average amount of income received by PKTD program workers before the wage intervention and after the PKTD program wage intervention.

Input variables are input variables or parameters in measuring the success or impact of implementing the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency. Variables are measured based on respondents' assessment of input variables consisting of indicators:

- The Program Socialization is by looking at respondents' perceptions regarding the implementation of PKTD program socialization in Gianyar Regency. The Program Socialization is carried out by examining how respondents perceive the execution of the PKTD program's socialization in Gianyar Regency. The main objective of the socialization implementation is to provide a clear understanding of the PKTD program, requirements, benefits, and procedures related to the PKTD program. Program socialization indicators are measured by calculating the number of

respondents who get PKTD (unit of people) program socialization.

- Program Target Accuracy is by looking at respondents' perceptions of the level of target accuracy to the extent to which the program has successfully targeted and provided assistance to individuals or groups in need and meet eligibility criteria. Target accuracy ensures that PKTD programs are delivered to those in need effectively, and have a significant impact on PKTD program recipients and rural communities. Target accuracy indicators are measured by counting respondents who feel the program is on target (units of people).
- The accuracy of the PKTD Program Wage Amount is by looking at respondents' perceptions of the accuracy of the program wage amount. The PKTD is a program that aims to provide temporary employment to people in need by paying cash wages. The accuracy of the amount of wages in the PKTD Program is very important so that this program is effective in providing benefits to workers in accordance with the availability of the program budget. The accuracy indicator of the amount of wages is measured by counting respondents who feel that the amount of daily wages of the PKTD program is right (units of people)

Process variables are variables related to the implementation during the PKTD program implemented in Gianyar Regency and the steps taken to achieve the program objectives. Variables are measured based on respondents' assessment of process variables consisting of indicators:

- Monitoring implementation by looking at respondents' perceptions of monitoring carried out by officers, monitoring implementation ensures that program implementation runs in accordance with the plans and objectives that have been set. Indicators of monitoring implementation are measured by calculating the number of respondents who get monitoring in the implementation of PKTD program (units of people).
- Companion Response Speed by looking at respondents' perceptions of the officer's response speed to complaints. The speed of response of PKTD program companions is critical to ensuring the effectiveness and success of the program. Escorts are responsible for providing support and guidance to CCP workers. The companion response speed indicator is measured by counting the number of respondents who feel how fast the response speed of the companion PKTD (unit of people) activities.
- PKTD program admission requirements by looking at respondents' perceptions regarding the ease of PKTD program admission requirements. The requirements as PKTD workers include the process of registering prospective program recipients and selection in determining who qualifies as workers with eligibility criteria applied consistently and objectively. The indicator of admission requirements is measured by counting the number of respondents who stated how easy the requirements are as recipients of the PKTD program (unit of people).

- Output variables are results or outputs produced by PKTD programs. These variables reflect the impact or observable outcomes of the program and are used to assess the extent to which the PKTD program successfully achieves its objectives. Variables are measured based on respondents' assessment of Output variables consisting of indicators:
- Achievement of Program Objectives is by looking at respondents' perceptions of how the implementation of the PKTD program is able to achieve the goals that have been set, by looking at workers who experience improved quality of life and increased income after being involved in the PKTD program. The objectives of the PKTD program may include providing better employment opportunities or higher incomes to some workers in the PKTD program. Goal achievement indicators are measured by calculating the number of respondents who feel the expected impact after receiving the PKTD (unit of people) program.
- Distribution of Program Assistance by looking at respondents' perceptions of how PKTD programs can be delivered to the right target. PKTD program distribution measures the extent to which PKTD programs are utilized by appropriate targets or those who meet established criteria, reflecting effectiveness in reaching and providing benefits to recipients in need. Indicators of PKTD program distribution can be measured by counting the number of respondents as PKTD recipients with predetermined criteria (units of people).
- Utilization of PKTD Program by looking at respondents' perceptions of how PKTD wage assistance can be used properly. The utilization of PKTD wage assistance measures the extent to which the PKTD program assistance provided can be utilized by program recipients effectively and in accordance with the objectives set. The PKTD Program Utilization Indicator can be measured by calculating the number of respondents who utilize PKTD wages appropriately (units of people)

C. Population & Sample

The population in this study is the recipient community of the Village Cash For Work program in Gianyar Regency in 2022, which is 719 people who receive the program. The sample size used in this study was determined using the Slovin formula. Through the Slovin formula, the number of samples can be calculated to analyze the effectiveness of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency. PKTD program recipient communities in Gianyar Regency are spread across 7 sub-districts and consist of 26 PKTD program recipient villages in Gianyar Regency. So the sample used in this study was 88 people who received the PKTD program. The way to choose samples or criteria taken in this study is to be the recipient community of the PKTD program in 2022.

D. Data Analysis Techniques

The data collection methods used in this study were observation methods, questionnaires, and in-depth interviews. The in-depth interview method in this study was used when seeking information to support or strengthen the results of this study. In-depth interviews to obtain information and extract information from key informants. The criteria for informant sources are beneficiaries of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency in 2022 and program beneficiaries who are

always actively participating in the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency in 2022.

The analysis techniques used consist of validity tests, reliability tests, descriptive analysis, normality tests, paired sample t-test difference tests, Wilcoxon Difference Tests and Analysis of the effectiveness of the Village Cash For Work program in Gianyar Regency. As for the descriptive analysis in this study to describe the level of effectiveness and weakness of the program, through questionnaire data collection and in-depth interviews, descriptive analysis helps describe the actual state (facts) of this study. The effectiveness formula includes:

$$\text{Effectiveness} = \frac{\text{Realization}}{\text{Target}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

IV. RESULTS OF ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of respondents showed that the number of PKTD program recipients in Gianyar Regency was sampled as many as 88 people. The number of respondents was divided into 26 villages that received the PKTD Program, where the most respondents were in Petak Village and LodtDownload Village which amounted to 11.36 percent.

Based on the results in the field, the number of male respondents is more than female respondents, namely male respondents totaling 68 people and female respondents totaling 20 people.

Age characteristics data shows that the number of respondents in the age group of 50-59 years is more than respondents in other age groups, which is 42.05 percent. The next most age group is the age group of 40-49 years, which is 32.95 percent. Table 4.3 shows that most PKTD program recipients are in the age range of 40-59 years which are still in the productive age group, so that when working and carrying out Cash Intensive activities can be carried out optimally.

The group of respondents based on education showed that the number of respondents with a higher level of high school education (graduated from high school) compared to other education levels was 76.14 percent, followed by junior high school (SMP) level education of 15.91 percent. The characteristics of respondents based on marital status can be explained that respondents in this study, namely PKTD Program recipient communities, are mostly married marital status of 96.59 percent.

Based on the results in the field, the main job owned by respondents in this study was work as a farmer, which was 31.82 percent, then followed by self-employed and laborer work 22.73 percent and 17.05 percent. The purpose of the PKTD program is as an empowerment program that utilizes local resources, labor and technology with the program targeting the unemployed, poor families, and marginalized communities which are priority programs by the government in efforts to alleviate poverty in rural areas.

Characteristics of PKTD Program Recipient Respondents Based on the Type of PKTD Activities shows that the types of PKTD activities carried out by respondents in Gianyar Regency are dominated by PKTD activities in the field of public infrastructure, which is 90.91 percent. The purpose of the program is to provide jobs to rural communities by paying wages in cash to reduce unemployment and encourage development in these rural areas.

Based on the results in the field, in the context of PKTD program work in the field of public infrastructure, several types of work are carried out such as: Village road construction which includes repair, maintenance or construction of roads in village areas to improve accessibility and connectivity between villages, as well as facilitating transportation and mobility of residents which can include road compaction, repair of damaged road surfaces, or even construction of new roads; Irrigation development to improve the agricultural irrigation system in the village and increase the productivity of the agricultural sector which can include the creation of new irrigation canals, repair or maintenance of existing irrigation canals, and construction of dams or reservoirs to regulate the flow of water, where with a good

irrigation system, agriculture in the village can be more efficient and productive.; Furthermore, maintenance of public facilities such as village halls and schools to improve infrastructure conditions in the village and provide better access for the community. In addition, in the PKTD program in the field of public infrastructure, other activities can also be carried out, such as bridge construction, procurement of street lighting, or making public trash cans. The aim is to improve village infrastructure in general and improve the quality of life of the community.

Furthermore, the average income of PKTD program recipients has increased income which can be observed from changes in each income class. Before the PKTD program was implemented, the majority of people had an average income smaller than Rp2000,000, but after the PKTD program, the number of people who had an average income smaller than Rp2000,000 decreased. In addition, there are also changes in income classes above Rp2000,000. Before the program there were only 2 people with income above Rp2000,000, but after the program, there were 16 people or about 18 percent with income classes above Rp2000,000. This shows a significant increase in the income of PKTD program recipients.

A. Normality Test

Table 2: Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov One-Sample Test on Income Before and Income After

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
	Pendapatan_Sebelum	Pendapatan_Sesudah
N	88	88
Test Statistic	.196	.097
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000 ^c	.040 ^c

Data processed (2023)

Table 2 can be seen that the results of the difference in normality test of one sample kolmogorov-Smirnov test show the results of the kolmogorov-smirnov test income before the implementation of the PKTD program of 0.196 with a significance level of 0.000 and the results of the kolmogorov-smirnov test of income after the implementation of the PKTD program of 0.097 with a significance level of 0.040. The

results of the normality test showed that both groups of data were not normally distributed by looking at the significance values of income before (0.000) and income after (0.040) < 0.05. The test method used for non-normally distributed data is the nonparametric difference test with the Wilcoxon difference test.

B. Wilcoxon difference test

Table 3: Wilcoxon signed rank test calculation results on Income Before and Income After

Test Statistics ^a	Pendapatan_Sesudah - Pendapatan_Sebelum
Z	-8.107 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on negative ranks.

Data processed (2023)

Based on Table 3 the income test results obtained by Zhitung are -8.107 with the probability of receiving Ho is 0.000 for a two-sided test (2-tailed) and divided by two for a one-sided test (1-tailed), this figure is still smaller than the level of significant or 0.000 < 0.05 so that Ho is rejected, it can be concluded that the community's income after the implementation of the PKTD Program is greater than before the implementation of the PKTD Program.

C. Analysis of the Effectiveness of the Village Cash For Work (PKTD) program in Gianyar Regency

In this study, to determine the effectiveness of the PKTD program, data collection techniques were used through questionnaires. The statements contained in the questionnaire are made based on indicators of each input, process, and output variable. To measure effectiveness regarding the variables asked whether they are effective or not, in this case effectiveness measurement standards are used according to

the reference to R & D Depdagri (1991), the standard measures used to measure effectiveness are divided into four, namely:

- < 40% = Very Ineffective;
- 40% - 59.9% = ineffective;
- 60% - 79.9% = moderately effective;
- > 80% = Very Effective.

The results of the analysis showed that the average score on the input variable was 3.71. This number means that the average respondent agrees and strongly agrees with the indicators in the input variable, namely X1.1, X1.2 and, X1.3. Based on these data, the effectiveness of the PKTD program on input variables can be described as follows.

$$\text{Effectiveness} = \frac{3,71}{4} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effectiveness} = 92,75\% \text{ (Highly Effective)}$$

Respondents' perception of input variables consisting of indicators of program socialization implementation, target accuracy level, accuracy of wages showed an effectiveness rate of 92.75 percent. This value is produced using a predetermined effectiveness formula, namely the realization value of 3.71 compared to the maximum achievement target value of 4, then the achievement of effectiveness of the input variable is 92.75 percent. Based on the effectiveness measurement standards according to the 1991 Depdagri R&D reference, a percentage of 92.75 percent is a very effective level of achievement. These results show that the PKTD program is very effective in meeting the expectations and needs of respondents.

The results of the analysis showed that the average score on the process variable was 3.61. This number means that the average respondent agrees and strongly agrees with the indicators in the input variables, namely X2.1, X2.2 and, X2.3. Based on these data, the effectiveness of the implementation of the PKTD program on input variables can be described as follows.

$$\text{Effectiveness} = \frac{3,61}{4} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effectiveness} = 90,25\% \text{ (Highly Effective)}$$

Respondents' perception of process variables consisting of indicators of monitoring implementation, companion response speed, and PKTD program acceptance requirements showed an effectiveness rate of 90.25 percent. This value is produced using a predetermined effectiveness formula, namely the realization value of 3.61 compared to the maximum achievement target value of 4, then the achievement of the effectiveness of the process variable is 90.25 percent. Based on the effectiveness measurement standard according to the 1991 Ministry of Agriculture R&D reference, a percentage of 90.25 percent is a very effective level of achievement.

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that the average score on the output variable is 3.78. This number means that the average respondent agrees and strongly agrees with the indicators in the process variables, namely X3.1, X3.2 and, X3.3. Based on these data, the effectiveness of the implementation of the PKTD program on process variables can be described as follows.

$$\text{Effectiveness} = \frac{3,78}{4} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Effectiveness} = 94,58\% \text{ (Highly Effective)}$$

Respondents' perception of output variables consisting of indicators of achieving program objectives, distributing program assistance, and utilizing PKTD programs showed an effectiveness rate of 94.58 percent. This value is produced using a predetermined effectiveness formula, namely the realization value of 3.78 compared to the maximum achievement target value of 4, then the achievement of effectiveness of the process variable is 94.58 percent. Based on the effectiveness measurement standard according to the 1991 Ministry of Agriculture R&D reference, a percentage of 94.58 percent is a very effective level of achievement.

D. Discussion of Community Income Level Results

In this study, a comparison was made between the income level of the community before and after the provision of PKTD program assistance. The results showed that after receiving the assistance, there was a significant increase in the income of the people in the village. This can be explained that with the PKTD program, new jobs are created in the village. Villagers have the opportunity to work in labor-intensive projects financed by the program. Thus, they can generate additional income that was previously unavailable. This increase in the number of jobs directly contributes to an increase in people's income.

Thus, based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that PKTD program assistance has a positive impact on increasing the income of people in the village. Therefore, continuous efforts are needed in the implementation of PKTD programs to improve the economic welfare of rural communities.

This discussion is supported by previous research by Sofi (2020), the results of the study concluded that PKTD in Pasuruan Regency and Probolinggo Regency in general runs well and is very useful in increasing people's income, especially the poor. The author also conveyed several inputs to overcome the obstacles faced in the implementation of the Village Fund PKT, first the Government needs to maintain the Village Fund PKT program because it is very useful for rural communities in order to increase direct community income, especially those who are unemployed or underemployed. In addition, this discussion is also supported by research conducted by Novanto (2023), the results of the study found that the implementation of PKTD in Wedi Village has succeeded in improving the welfare of rural communities, where PKTD in general runs well and is beneficial in increasing community income. This is supported by a positive response from the village community, especially the local workforce.

E. Discussion of Program Effectiveness Input Variables

Respondents' perception of input variables consisting of indicators of program socialization implementation, target accuracy level, accuracy of wages showed an effectiveness rate of 92.75 percent. Based on the effectiveness measurement standards according to the 1991 Depdagri R&D reference, a percentage of 92.75 percent is a very effective level of achievement. These results show that the PKTD

program is very effective in meeting the expectations and needs of respondents. Indicators of program socialization implementation are one of the factors that contribute positively to respondents' perceptions. This shows that the socialization carried out to introduce the program has gone well, so that respondents have an adequate understanding of the objectives and benefits of the program. In addition, the level of target accuracy is also an important factor that contributes to respondents' perception. Programs that successfully achieve predetermined goals give respondents confidence that the program is effective in delivering the desired benefits. The accuracy of the amount of wages is also an indicator that influences respondents' perception of the effectiveness of the program. If the amount of wages given is as expected by respondents, this will provide satisfaction and indicate the success of the program in providing the right wages.

F. Discussion of Program Effectiveness Process Variables

Respondents' perception of process variables consisting of indicators of monitoring implementation, companion response speed, and PKTD program acceptance requirements showed an effectiveness rate of 90.25 percent. Based on the effectiveness measurement standard according to the 1991 Depdagri R&D reference, a percentage of 90.25 percent is a very effective achievement rate. Indicators of monitoring implementation are important factors that contribute to respondents' perceptions. Well-conducted monitoring shows that the PKTD program is continuously monitored and evaluated to ensure proper implementation. The speed of the companion response also had a significant influence on respondents' perceptions of the effectiveness of the PKTD program. If the companion responds quickly to questions or requests from program recipients, this indicates that the PKTD program is paying adequate attention to participants. In this context, the speed of response of companions provides an indication of the success of the program in providing timely and relevant support. PKTD program admission requirements also play an important role in respondents' perceptions of effectiveness. If the program admission requirements set are affordable and in accordance with the needs of respondents, this provides ease of access and wider participation in the program.

G. Discussion of Program Effectiveness Output Variables

Respondents' perception of output variables consisting of indicators of achieving program objectives, distributing program assistance, and utilizing PKTD programs showed an effectiveness rate of 94.58 percent. Based on the effectiveness measurement standard according to the 1991 Ministry of Agriculture R&D reference, a percentage of 94.58 percent is a very effective achievement level. The indicator of achieving program objectives is one of the main factors contributing to the positive perception of respondents. If the PKTD program successfully achieves the goals that have been set, it shows that the program is effective in achieving the desired results. The distribution of program assistance also affects respondents' perceptions of the effectiveness of the PKTD program. If program assistance is distributed well, on time, and on target, it gives respondents confidence that the program is able to provide real and relevant support for them. The utilization of PKTD programs is also an important

indicator in measuring effectiveness. If this program is successfully utilized by respondents optimally and in accordance with program objectives, this shows that the PKTD program has a significant impact and provides sustainable benefits.

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that the PKTD program has a very high level of effectiveness in meeting the expectations and needs of respondents. The effectiveness rate of implementing the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency is classified as very effective with an average effectiveness of 92.53 percent.

This discussion is supported by previous research conducted by Kurnia (2021), it was found that: the implementation of PKTD in Jembrana Regency has met the effective criteria, from the perspective of empowerment, the implementation of PKTD has been quite effective. The goal to be achieved is to be able to empower the poor, unemployed and underemployed groups has been achieved. These results also support Setiawan's (2022) research on the evaluation of the Cash Intensive Labor policy in Pekarungan village, Sukodono District, Sidoarjo Regency, stating that the PKTD policy in Pekarungan Village has been effective in empowering marginalized communities in the village and developing a sense of mutual cooperation and community participation in Pekarungan Village, besides that it has also been effective in creating job opportunities even though it is only temporary.

H. Weaknesses of the Cash For Work (PKTD) program in Gianyar Regency

Based on research conducted using in-depth interviews, there are several weaknesses in the PKTD program. This in-depth interview was conducted to gain a deeper understanding of the implementation of PKTD programs in the field, involving related parties, namely program participants. The results of this study provide a more comprehensive picture of the weaknesses present in the PKTD program and provide a better understanding of its impact on participants and communities at the village level. With this understanding, efforts to improve and improve the PKTD program can be carried out more precisely and effectively, in order to provide greater benefits to rural communities in need. Some weaknesses in the PKTD program include lack of training and skill development, as well as lack of commitment and seriousness in implementing the PKTD program.

Training and skills development in PKTD program can provide greater long-term benefits for participants.

"Well, in my opinion, the main weakness is the lack of skills possessed by the villagers. In some cases, there are jobs that require professionals or specific skills that cannot be done without prior training. I think that villagers should get training before getting involved in this program. With this training too, they can gain broader skills, not just limited to simple jobs, for example being able to engage as a direct handyman, not just helping to carry sand, or simple work. That way, the community will have wider job opportunities after the program is completed. In addition, through the development of these skills, the PKTD program can provide sustainable

benefits to rural communities, by increasing their capacity and helping to improve their economic conditions in the future." explained Mr. I Wayan Kuasa Adi Putra, a PKTD program worker as the head handyman, who is directly involved in working on the PKTD program in Saba Village, Blahbatuh District, Gianyar Regency. (23/05/2023)

Factors such as ignorance of long-term benefits, lack of motivation, or lack of understanding of their responsibilities as program participants can be the cause of not serious implementation of the project.

"In my opinion, if the weakness lies in how we can communicate to the community that this PKTD program is a good program for the benefit of the community itself where the community can manage, can be as workers, and the community itself has the location of the area to be managed. In my opinion, it is how to communicate so that the community welcomes that the PKTD work carried out will have a long-term impact, because what is managed is the location of the village area, enjoyed by the community. Because sometimes people don't think that far, so the work on this program is sometimes less serious. With this communicative and participatory approach, I believe that the community will be more welcoming and serious in carrying out Cash For Work projects. All parties need to work together to ensure that this program provides long-term benefits to the community and encourage collective awareness in implementing programs that prioritize mutual cooperation and active participation of rural communities". explained Mr. I Wayan Sudiawan, a PKTD program worker as the head handyman, who is directly involved in working on the PKTD program in Petak Village, Gianyar District, Gianyar Regency. (29/05/2023).

I. Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the results of the analysis, it is concluded that 1. Community income after the implementation of the PKTD program is greater than before the implementation of the PKTD program; 2. The effectiveness rate of the implementation of the PKTD program in Gianyar Regency is classified as very effective with an average effectiveness of 92.53 percent. 3. The weakness of The Village Cash For Work Program (PKTD) lies in the lack of training and skill development in the program, in some cases there are jobs that require specific skills, so that training and skill development are needed in the PKTD program to provide opportunities for people to engage in more complex work and potentially generate better income. In addition, lack of commitment and seriousness in implementing the PKTD program is also a weakness of the program. Factors such as ignorance of long-term benefits, lack of motivation, or lack of understanding of their responsibilities as program participants can be the cause of not taking the project seriously.

Because the PKTD program has a very effective level of effectiveness and a positive impact on people's income, it indicates that this PKTD program is worth continuing. It is necessary to conduct continuous monitoring and evaluation of the PKTD program to ensure the sustainability of community income after the program ends. This involves

careful planning of long-term funding and close supervision of program implementation.

The government should strengthen the training and skills development component in the PKTD program. By providing training tailored to the needs of the community, people will have the opportunity to engage in more complex work and potentially generate better income.

To increase the commitment and seriousness of participants, intensive educational efforts are needed about the long-term benefits of PKTD programs and responsibilities as PKTD recipients. In addition, providing appropriate incentives and showing positive results from the PKTD program can increase participant motivation.

Collaboration with related parties such as training institutions, universities, and the private sector can enrich the implementation of PKTD programs. Through cross-sectoral and cross-program cooperation, resources can be optimally utilized to provide more effective mentoring, training, and guidance

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